

An Adaptive Equivalent Consumption Minimization Strategy for Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles Based on Traffic Information

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Abstract: Energy management strategies play an important role in performance optimization of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), and can be further improved by incorporating external traffic information. Motivated by this, an adaptive equivalent consumption minimization strategy considering traffic information is proposed in this study to facilitate the effective energy management of PHEVs. First, the initial equivalent factors in terms of different initial state of charge (SOC) and driving distance are searched by genetic algorithm. Then, the simplified dynamic programming is leveraged to determine the optimal SOC trajectory according to the traffic information with fast calculation speed. The fuzzy controller is employed to regulate the equivalent factor dynamically, thus enabling effective tracking of the reference SOC trajectory. A hardware-in-the-loop simulation platform based on the virtual scene is developed to validate the performance of controller. Simulation and experimental results highlight that the proposed strategy can lead to less fuel consumption, compared to traditional equivalent consumption minimization strategy, thereby proving its feasibility.

Key words: Adaptive equivalent consumption minimization strategy (A-ECMS), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), reference state of charge (SOC) trajectory, traffic information.

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

PHEVs	plug-in hybrid electric vehicles
EVs	electric vehicles
HEVs	hybrid electric vehicles

AER	all-electric range
EMS	energy management strategy
SOC	state of charge
GA	genetic algorithm
ITS	intelligent transportation system
GPS	global positioning system
GIS	geographic information system
IOV	internet-of-vehicle
DP	dynamic programming
RL	reinforcement learning
QP	quadratic programming
PMP	Pontryagin's minimum principle
ICE	internal combustion engine
SA	simulated annealing
NN	neural network
GT	game theory
ECMS	equivalent consumption minimization strategy
EF	equivalent factor
A-ECMS	adaptive equivalent consumption minimization strategy
HIL	hardware-in-the-loop
ISG	integrated starter/generator
DCT	dual clutch transmission
RC	resistance–capacitance
NEDC	new European driving cycle
FCD	floating car data
CS	charge sustaining

Symbols

I	battery current
$E(SOC)$	open circuit voltage
$R(SOC)$	internal resistance of the battery
P_b	battery output power
SOC_0	initial value of the state-of-charge
Q_0	battery capacity
x	state variable

u	control variable
J	cost function
T_m	engine torque
T_e	motor torque
H	Hamiltonian function
\dot{m}_{fuel}	fuel rate
λ	co-state
s	equivalent factor
Q_{lhv}	calorific value of the fuel
\dot{m}_{ele}	equivalent fuel rate of battery power
P_{bat}	battery power
L	fitness function
e_{SOC}	difference between the reference state of charge and actual value
n_p	engine speed
s_{add}	equivalent factor variation
s_{ini}	initial equivalent factor
R_{target}	driving distance
φ	mapping function

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increase of vehicles and massive consumption of petroleum resources, energy crisis, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and environmental pollution have incurred widespread concern [1, 2]. Developing environmental friendly transportation tools supplies a possible manner to mitigate the existing problems. Transportation electrification have been proved to be an effective developing direction, of which the main research focus includes battery electric vehicles (BEVs), fuel cell vehicles and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) [3]. Plug-in HEVs (PHEVs), as a combination of BEVs and HEVs, can fully merge both advantages of a certain all-electric range (AER) and superior fuel efficiency improvement [4]. The key technologies regarding PHEVs includes proper design of powertrain components associated with the power allocation amongst the main components, referred to as energy management strategies (EMSs) [5].

EMSs have been widely researched by industry and academia. With the development of modern communication technologies and positioning systems, more and more information can be referred to assist in

improving the energy management performance of PHEVs [6, 7]. Generally, EMSs are mainly classified into three categories: rule based, global optimization based, and instantaneous optimization based [8]; and the optimization target can be different, including fuel economy improvement, battery lifespan extension, and reduction of the calculation intensity [9, 10].

Rule based EMSs decide operating modes and energy distribution rules of power sources mainly based on experience and characteristics of each powertrain component [11]. Typical inner formats of the strategy can be deterministic rules or fuzzy rule tables. Usually, the vehicle power demand and battery state of charge (SOC) [12] are regarded as the referred parameters, and operating states and actions of the engine and electric motor are recommended according to the predetermined rules [13, 14]. Actually, how to properly design an effective rule-based algorithm still remains challenging. Extraction of rules based on experience is time-consuming and laborious, and the actual application effect cannot be guaranteed all the time. Similar difficulties are also encountered when referring fuzzy logic to design the rule based EMS. Genetic algorithm (GA) is employed to optimize membership functions of the fuzzy logic controller to achieve better fuel economy and lower emission [15, 16]. In addition, traffic information can supply useful reference for adjustment and update of rules. Refs. [16, 17] propose the adaptive rule-based algorithm by sufficiently absorbing traffic information.

Global optimization based EMSs can optimize the energy consumption according to the wholly known driving conditions [18]. Intelligent transportation system (ITS), global positioning system (GPS), geographic information system (GIS), and internet-of-vehicle (IOV) technologies are the most common media to supply global driving conditions [19, 20]. Among all the candidates, dynamic programming (DP) [21], reinforcement learning (RL) [22], quadratic programming (QP) [23] and Pontryagin's minimum principle (PMP) [24] are the representatives. DP has been applied widely due to its easy simplification when faced with high nonlinear discrete problems [25]. RL, as an extension of DP, can find the optimal solution on the basis of construction of the state probability function [26]. QP can find the optimal solution in the light of energy distribution only if the cost function can be described as a bunch of quadratic equations [27]. PMP has been widely applied when the object function (usually minimization of the fuel consumption) can be expressed in a deterministic manner, and meanwhile the constraints can be sufficiently considered [28]. Even the global optimization based EMSs are capable of finding the optimal power allocation among different sources in a certain trip. However, modeling of the vehicle power system is quite complex and calculation of the algorithm is time and memory intensive,

undoubtedly limiting its online application [29]. Moreover, they are difficult, and even impossible, to adapt to the dynamically varying driving condition. A main contribution of global optimization EMSs is that the solved result can be treated as a benchmark to evaluate other algorithms' performance [19, 30, 31].

To overcome limitations of global optimization algorithms, instantaneous optimization based EMSs are spurred with or without relying on the traffic information. The instantaneous optimization based EMSs can allocate the power of internal combustion engine (ICE) and battery in real time, by considering the current driving condition and status of the vehicle, to minimize the energy cost/ consumption in each moment. Some intelligent optimization algorithms, such as simulated annealing (SA) [32], neural networks (NNs) [33] and game theory (GT) [34], are widely adopted to achieve instantaneous optimization in view of different targets including fuel economy improvement, battery life extension, and exhaust emission deduction. One of the representatives belongs to equivalent consumption minimization strategies (ECMSs) due to its capability of direct immediate optimization. To exploit ECMSs, a key challenge is to properly determine the equivalent factor (EF) [35]. Refs. [36, 37] reveal that the EF can be influenced by the varying characteristics of power components and traffic information, such as initial SOC, driving distance/duration and driving condition. Some investigations have been conducted to regulate the EF in an adaptive manner, referred to the adaptive ECMS, according to the vehicle velocity profile and driving conditions [38]. In [39], instead of direct estimation of ECMS optimal equivalent factor, this brief derives estimation for the upper and lower bounds of the optimal EF. Usually, traffic information cannot be fully attained in the beginning and prediction of the vehicle velocity in a limited horizon can be potentially beneficial. Popular solutions include Markov chain [40] and NNs [41]. Ref. [42] proposes a data-driven ECMS that determines the EF based on neural network, compares two forecasting methods including the Markov chain model and the back propagation NN (BPNN) based on real driving cycles, showcasing superiority of the Markov chain especially in computational efficiency. In addition, it should be noted that instantaneous optimization based EMSs can achieve the instantaneous optimal energy allocation; however, they may not be optimal from the global perspective.

As discussed above, the instantaneous optimization EMSs with the reference of traffic information, which is imperative for global optimization, can potentially improve the energy allocation efficiency in the global viewpoint [43]. In other words, effective combination of instantaneous optimization and global planning may outperform the traditional individual instantaneous EMS. Motivated by this, we distinguish our endeavor in the

research of the A-ECMS based on traffic information. On the basis of insightful analysis of traditional ECMS, an A-ECMS with full consideration of traffic information is proposed in this study. To attain the adaptive regulation of the EF, a nonlinear relationship among the EF, driving distance and initial SOC is built by GA. Subsequently, the global traffic information is achieved by smoothing the average speed value of the trip, and as a result, the reference SOC trajectory can be planned. Furthermore, a fuzzy controller is harnessed to adaptively regulate the EF with the inputs of the difference between the reference SOC and actual value, engine speed and initial EF. Finally, the feasibility of proposed strategy is verified by numerical simulation. In addition, experimental validation based on the proposed strategy is carried out by a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) platform with virtual scene. The experimental results show that the fuel economy based on the proposed A-ECMS can be improved by 6.01% in comparison with that of the typical ECMS without traffic information, verifying the effectiveness of the proposed strategy. The main contribution distinguishing the endeavor in this study is that a real-time control framework by incorporating the A-ECMS and traffic information is built, and sufficient validation is performed by the integrated simulation and HIL experiment, respectively.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the powertrain structure and system model are formulated. In Section III, the proposed A-ECMS is detailed with mathematical analysis. Section IV conducts the simulation validation as well as the HIL validation with the proposed A-ECMS, DP and the traditional ECMS, and Section VI draws the main conclusions of this study.

II. POWERTRAIN STRUCTURE AND SYSTEM MODEL

The plug-in hybrid powertrain system studied in this research belongs to a parallel topology, as shown in Fig. 1. The system is mainly composed of the engine, integrated starter/generator (ISG) motor, main clutch C1, dual clutch transmission (DCT), battery pack, and inverter. The engine and ISG motor are the power sources, and both can work individually or jointly. The ISG motor is placed before the input of transmission and is coupled with the engine shaft by the clutch to achieve the power coupling. The main clutch is located between the engine and ISG motor, and the DCT is harnessed to change the speed and torque according to the driving demand.

Fig. 1. Plug-in hybrid powertrain system.

In this research, the system model mainly consists of the engine, ISG motor, battery, and transmission. The theoretical method and experimental method are employed together to model the powertrain in detail.

A. Engine Model

The engine model includes the fuel consumption model and efficiency model. The fuel consumption model is applied to calculate the fuel rate under the condition of steady speed and torque, as shown in Fig. 2 (a); and the efficiency model is employed to analyze the operating efficiency with the inputs of torque and speed, as shown in Fig. 2 (b).

Fig. 2. The engine model. (a) Engine fuel consumption model; (b) The engine efficiency model.

B. ISG Motor Model

The ISG motor can be viewed as a motor to output the mechanical torque; and can also be served as a generator to charge the battery. In this research, the motor model is built by the numerical modeling method. The motor efficiency and speed characteristics are acquired by interpolating the experimental test data, as shown

in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. ISG motor model. (a) ISG efficiency; (b) ISG speed characteristics.

C. Battery Model

By taking simplification, effectiveness and precision into account, two typical models, referred to as the internal resistance (Rint) model and resistance–capacitance (RC) model, are commonly employed to characterize the battery electric performances [44]. Compared with the Rint model, the RC model is slightly more complex and computational intensive. On this account, the Rint model is adopted due to its simplicity and acceptable precision. It is necessary to mention that the battery temperature is assumed unchanged, and thus the temperature influence on the battery is neglected. The relationship between the electromotive force and internal resistance of the battery with different SOC is plotted in Fig. 4. As can be seen, the electromotive force increases from 290 V to 347 V when SOC varies from 0 to 1; and likewise, the internal resistance varies with SOC in both charge and discharge condition and reaches the minimum value when the SOC is near 0.5.

Fig. 4. The electromotive force and internal resistance of battery. (a) Electromotive force; (b) Internal resistance.

Based on the Rint model, the battery current I can be calculated, as:

$$I = \frac{E(SOC) - \sqrt{E(SOC)^2 - 4R(SOC)P_b}}{2R(SOC)} \quad (1)$$

where $E(SOC)$ is the open circuit voltage, $R(SOC)$ is the internal resistance of the battery, and P_b denotes the battery power. The battery SOC, as a critical control parameter of EMS, not only reflects the remaining capacity, but also determines the internal resistance, voltage, and operating efficiency of the battery. In this study, the coulomb counting method is adopted to calculate the SOC, as:

$$SOC = SOC_0 - \frac{\int_{t_0}^t I(\tau) d\tau}{Q_0} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where SOC_0 denotes the initial value of the SOC and Q_0 expresses the battery capacity.

D. Transmission Model

In this study, we only consider the influence of efficiency and ratio when modeling the transmission system. The efficiency is supposed to be 0.92, and the transmission ratio and final drive ratio are shown in Table I.

Table I Gear ratio

Parameters	Value
1 st -6 th gear ratio $i1/ i2 /i3 i4/ i5/ i6$	3.917/2.429/1.436 1.021/0.848/0.667
Final drive ratio $ia1/ ia2$	3.762/4.158

III. ADAPTIVE EQUIVALENT CONSUMPTION MINIMIZATION STRATEGY

A. Problem Analysis and ECMS Application

The essence of ECMS is to convert the energy consumed by battery into the equivalent fuel consumption. The torque distribution scheme that minimizes the instantaneous equivalent fuel consumption is assigned as an preferable solution to engine and motor [45]. By taking the battery SOC as state variable x associated with the engine torque and gear ratio as the control variable u , and considering the minimum fuel consumption as the optimization target, the energy management is a typical optimization problem that can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \min J(u, x) \\ s.t. \begin{cases} x_{\min} \leq x \leq x_{\max} \\ u_{\min} \leq u \leq u_{\max} \end{cases} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where the superscripts min and max denotes the minimum and maximum values of each variable, respectively.

The cost function can be expressed as:

$$J(u, x) = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t)) dt \quad (4)$$

where \dot{m}_{fuel} denotes the fuel rate, and t_0 and t_f express the beginning and ending time in a certain trip.

The dynamic characteristics of the state variable can be formulated as:

$$\dot{x} = -\frac{E(SOC) - \sqrt{E(SOC)^2 - 4R(SOC)P_b}}{2R(SOC)Q_0} = f(x, P_m) \quad (5)$$

In addition, the following constraints should be imposed, as:

$$\begin{cases} SOC_{\min} \leq SOC \leq SOC_{\max} \\ P_{b_min} \leq P_b \leq P_{b_max} \\ T_{m_min} \leq T_m \leq T_{m_max} \\ T_{e_min} \leq T_e \leq T_{e_max} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Consequently, the Hamiltonian function can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} H(x, \lambda, u, t) &= \lambda \cdot f(x, P_b, t) + \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t)) \\ &= \lambda(t)\dot{x}(t) + \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t), t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where λ denotes the co-state of Hamiltonian function. In our previous research, the co-state is related with the battery OCV and internal resistance [38]. To more intuitively describe the equivalent relationship between the electricity consumption and fuel consumption, the EF s is usually defined as:

$$s = -\lambda \cdot \frac{Q_{lhv}}{E(SOC) \cdot Q_0} \quad (8)$$

where Q_{lhv} is the calorific value of the fuel. Now, equation (7) can be transformed into:

$$\begin{aligned} H(x, s, u, t) &= \dot{m}_{ele}(t) + \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t)) \\ &= s(t) \frac{P_b(t)}{H_{LHV}} + \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\dot{m}_{ele}(t)$ denotes the equivalent fuel rate of the battery power. Actually, equation (9) is essentially the key function of the ECMS, and its physical meaning indicates the instantaneous fuel consumption of vehicle.

B. A-ECMS Application

As mentioned above, the driving distance, initial SOC and driving condition show much influence on decision of optimal EF. Actually, these three factors should be comprehensively considered when determining the EF. Currently, the future traffic information can be acquired from ITS via the vehicle-mounted

interconnection system. In this manner, the global driving information can be obtained and consequently, the EF can be optimized. As a result, the effect of ECMS for PHEV can be fully exploited. In this context, an A-ECMS based on traffic information is proposed in this study, as depicted in Fig. 5. It mainly consists of the following three parts:

Fig. 5. A-ECMS based on traffic information.

1) Optimization of the initial EF based on GA. First, the new European driving cycle (NEDC) is taken as the experimental condition without considering influence of different driving cycles on the EF. The optimal EFs is estimated by GA with respect to different initial SOC and driving distances, and the relationship among them under the NEDC is constructed. GA is capable of finding the nonlinear optimal values through a series of actions including selection, crossover and mutation. The reason of selecting NEDC as the initial driving cycle is that NEDC includes the high speed and low speed section, and it is similar to actual driving conditions in China [46].

2) Design of the reference SOC trajectory based on traffic information. The traffic information in the future mileage obtained by ITS is processed to build the approximate global driving condition. On this basis, the global reference SOC trajectory can be determined through the simplified DP, which is explained in detail in our previous research [47]. In short, the simplified DP is achieved by fitting the efficiency model of engine and

motor by two quadratic equations and reducing the control degree-of-freedom from two to one. By this manner, the calculation time can be greatly reduced without discounting the optimization effects.

3) Correction of the EF based on the fuzzy logic controller. When the vehicle runs, the real-time SOC reference can be obtained by interpolating the reference SOC trajectory. The EF is adaptively adjusted by the fuzzy controller according to the reference SOC value, actual SOC feedback and engine speed. The equivalent fuel consumption is calculated according to the optimal EF. Furthermore, the optimal torque distribution scheme is constructed to realize track of the SOC trajectory and meanwhile improve the fuel economy of vehicle.

1) Optimization of Initial Equivalent Factor Based on GA

The EF correlates with the driving distances and initial SOC. Actually, the EF optimization is a nonlinear global optimization problem that can be effectively tackled by GA. The basic principle of GA is to simulate natural selection and biological evolution process of the nature. Generally, GA includes a series of actions such as crossover, mutation and elite selection [48]. The optimization process of EFs based on GA used is sketched in Fig. 6. More detailed calculation can be found in [49] and references therein. Here, the fitness function is the same as stated in (4), i.e., the total fuel consumption.

Fig. 6. Optimization process of the EF based on GA.

Additionally, the influence induced by the driving condition on the EF is analyzed. The initial SOC is set to 0.8, the driving distance is set to 50 km and in this premise, simulations are respectively conducted based on the NEDC and US06 cycle. The corresponding SOC variation is sketched in Fig. 7. When the simulations are performed, the optimal EF is set to 2.74 and 2.73 for attaining the similar SOC variation trend. Different driving conditions can lead to different EFs, and yes, the driving condition can generate a certain influence on the optimal EF. However, the optimal initial EF calculated based on the NEDC will be adaptively adjusted in the fuzzy logic module to compensate the difference incurred by different driving conditions.

Fig. 7. The influence on the EF arisen by the driving distance.

To calculate the EF regarding different initial SOC and driving distances, multiple simulations are conducted by supposing that the initial SOC ranges from 0.4 to 1.0 and the driving distance varies from 0 to 100 km. Similar as that introduced in [50], the relationship, as plotted in Fig. 8, can be described by interpolation of the experimental results.

Fig. 8. Relationship between driving distance, initial SOC and initial equivalent factor.

2) Reference SOC Trajectory Planning Based on Traffic Information

A group of detailed traffic information can be acquired by ITS. Typical information usually includes the traffic signal status, traffic flow, average velocity of traffic flow, pedestrian status, etc. Among these factors, the average velocity of traffic flow can directly reflect the global driving condition, whereas the rest would influence the speed variation indirectly. On this basis, the study focuses on obtaining the reference SOC trajectory through only the average velocity information of traffic flow, which is calculated by dividing the whole driving distance over the average duration. For convenience, we assume that the average velocity of the traffic flow is updated every 200 s. The future driving distance is divided into a number of sections with each length of 200 m, and thus the average velocity of the traffic flow in one section can be represented by the mean value of the velocity of all vehicles inside the current section. However, the average velocity of the floating car data (FCD) appears like a piecewise function in the spatial domain, which is not consistent with the actual situation. In this study, a one-order low filter is introduced to smooth the average velocity, as shown in Fig. 9. By this manner, the step change phenomenon of the average velocity can be smoothed to exhibit continuous variation.

Fig. 9. Average speed of traffic flow and its smoothing result.

As noted above, proper simplification of the DP when planning the SOC trajectory can reduce the computational intensity. As a reference, a combined driving cycle with the duration of 5551 s is built which consists of WVUSUB, MANHATTAN, 1015, UDDS, and HWFET, covering different types of road conditions. As shown in Fig. 10, the proposed simplified DP can finish planning the similar SOC trajectory of the combined driving cycle within 28.23 s with a laptop of the CPU Core i5 and the 16 gigabytes memory, and the absolute value of error is limited in 0.0163, compared to the conventional DP.

Fig. 10. The reference SOC trajectory.

3) Correction of EF Based on the Fuzzy Controller

A common knowledge is that the global optimal control of EMSs cannot be achieved by applying only the fixed EF. In this study, the EF is dynamically regulated according to the designed reference SOC trajectory, engine speed and initial SOC. The calculation of EF mainly consists of two parts: 1) the initial EF which is considered the driving distance and initial SOC, and 2) the modified EF that is calculated from the reference SOC trajectory. The former can be solved by looking up the mapping table, as shown in Fig. 8, with respect to the driving distance and initial SOC. The latter is usually treated as a typical trajectory following problem. As a consequence, the typical proportional-integral-differential (PID) control and fuzzy control are the representative methods for this kind of problem. Considering the computation complexity and controlling precision, the fuzzy controller is employed to modulate the EF dynamically for tracking the reference SOC trajectory.

In terms of fuzzy control, the magnitude of the input and output variables is described by words. Undoubtedly, more selection of the states can describe variables more accurately and leads to higher controlling accuracy; however, the price to pay is the complex classification process and complicated rule design. To trade off the controlling performance and the calculation complexity, three words, i.e., big, medium and small, are generally referred to describe the state of input and output variables of the fuzzy controller. In addition, the positive and negative directions of each word and the state of zero are also considered. As such, there are in total seven words existing in the fuzzy logic set, namely negative small (NS), negative medium (NM), negative large (NL), zero (ZO), positive small (PS), positive middle (PM), positive big (PB). In this study, the input variables of fuzzy control are the difference between the reference SOC and actual SOC e_{soc} as well as the engine speed n_p , and the output is the equivalent factor variation s_{add} . The Gaussian function is selected as

the membership function, the actual variation range and linguistic values of each variable are listed in Table II, and the corresponding fuzzy rules are detailed in Table III. The characteristic map of fuzzy control input and output is shown in Fig. 11.

Table II The universe and lingual variables for each variable

Variable	Variation range	Linguistic variables
e_{SOC}	(-0.01, +0.01)	(NB, NM, NS, ZO, PS, PM, PB)
n_p	(0, 6000)	(S, M, B)
s_{add}	(-0.5, +0.5)	(NB, NM, NS, ZO, PS, PM, PB)

Table III The fuzzy rules

Variable	State																
e_{SOC}	NB	NM	NM	NM	NS	NS	NS	ZO	ZO	ZO	PS	PS	PS	PM	PM	PM	PB
n_p	/	S	B	M	S	B	M	S	B	M	S	B	M	S	B	M	/
s_{add}	NB	NB	NS	NM	NM	ZO	NS	NS	PS	ZO	ZO	PM	PS	PS	PB	PM	PB

Fig. 11. Characteristic map of fuzzy control input and output.

The correction process of the EF is detailed as follows:

1) At the beginning of the trip, the initial SOC and driving distance are imported to calculate the initial EF

s_{ini} based on GA, as:

$$s_{ini} = \varphi_1(SOC_0, R_{target}) \quad (10)$$

where R_{target} is the driving distance, and φ_1 is the mapping function.

2) The initial EF would be further controlled to adapt to the real traffic condition by referring the planned SOC trajectory. The corrected difference of EF $s_{add}(t)$, calculated in (11), is leveraged as the input to regulate the SOC to track the reference.

$$s_{add}(t) = \varphi_2(e_{soc}(t), n_p(t)) \quad (11)$$

where $e_{soc}(t)$ denotes the difference between the reference SOC and actual value, $n_p(t)$ is the engine speed, and φ_2 is the mapping function illustrated in Fig. 11.

3) The updated EF $s(t)$ after correction can be calculated, as:

$$s(t) = s_{ini} + s_{add}(t) \quad (12)$$

4) On this basis, the Hamiltonian function is updated accordingly, as:

$$H(x, s, u, t, R) = (s_{ini} + s_{add}(u, R, t)) \cdot f(x, u, t) + \dot{m}_{fuel}(u(t)) \quad (13)$$

5) The equivalent fuel consumption is calculated based on the modified Hamiltonian equation, and the torque distribution of the engine and motor is distributed according to the calculation result. Meanwhile, the current battery SOC and driving distance are obtained to form the closed loop control of EF.

IV. SIMULATION AND HIL VALIDATION

A. The Integrated Simulation Validation

In the study, the integrated simulation is conducted to verify the feasibility of the proposed strategy. The required traffic information data should be obtained from ITS. However, due to infeasibility of direct acquisition of navigation system, the research adopts a virtual software, VISSIM, to construct a virtual traffic scene, shown in Fig. 12, thereby simulating the real driving condition.

The velocity of the virtual vehicle is shown in Fig. 13, and the entire trip distance together with the speed variation is shown in Fig. 14, wherein the solid black line indicates the actual driving trajectory of the target vehicle. The target vehicle starts at around 2800 s, and reaches the destination after 2895 s. First, the road is congested, the velocity is low; and then the vehicle enters the expressway, the speed increases rapidly. Between two sections of the expressway, a traffic jam is encountered. Finally, the vehicle leaves the expressway and reaches the destination.

Fig. 12. The simulation traffic scene in VISSIM.

Fig. 13. The data of the virtual vehicle.

Fig. 14. The segment average speed in VISSIM traffic environment.

The proposed A-ECMS can take the full traffic information into account. To further validate the feasibility of the proposed algorithm, the proposed algorithm with the EF adaptively regulated by the proportional-integral

(PI) controller and fuzzy logic controller is simulated, respectively. The calculated EF and varied SOC trajectory are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. It can be clearly observed that without considering the traffic information, the EF cannot dynamically change with the external driving environment. The battery SOC drops to 0.3 at 2450 s, and the vehicle enters into the charge sustaining (CS) mode. To maintain the SOC in the vicinity of low threshold, the engine has to be started in the low-efficiency zone, thus resulting in more fuel consumption, as shown in Table IV. On the contrary, when employing the A-ECMS by considering the traffic information, the reference SOC trajectory varies with the traffic information. The adaptive adjustment of EF enables that the SOC can finally converge to 0.3 in the end of trip. The vehicle does not enter into the CS mode; and moreover, the SOC trajectory is quite close to that solved by DP. As can also be seen, when the fuzzy logic controller can regulate the EF to vary more smoothly than the PI controller. Table IV compares the operation cost, and we can find that the proposed A-ECMS can save 10.98% of the corrected fuel consumption, compared to the traditional ECMS. However, it is still 5.8% higher than that of DP. Additionally, as can be seen from Table IV, when the fuzzy logic is applied to adaptively regulate the EF, the proposed A-ECMS can gain less fuel consumption, compared to that based on the PI controller. The reason is that when the difference between the reference SOC and actual value is limited, the integral term of PI controller still takes effect and thus leads to further derivation of the reference trajectory of SOC. While the fuzzy logic can omit the integral term existing in the PI controller. By choosing different rules according to the SOC difference and vehicle speed set in the fuzzy logic controller, the EF can be finally regulated to enable the effective track of the referred SOC, thereby attaining better energy management between the battery and engine.

Fig. 15. Comparison of equivalent factors.

Fig. 16. Comparison of SOC curves.

Table IV Comparison of operating costs in the simulation test

	Fuel Consumption (kg)	Ending SOC	Corrected Fuel Consumption (kg)
ECMS	0.1889	0.2991	0.1930
A-ECMS (PI)	0.1718 (-9.05%)	0.2987 (-0.13%)	0.1743 (-9.69%)
A-ECMS (Fuzzy)	0.1688 (-10.64%)	0.2984 (-0.23%)	0.1718 (-10.98%)
DP	0.1659 (-12.16%)	0.3028 (+1.91%)	0.1606 (-16.78%)

Note: +: Increment; -: Reduction

B. Hardware-in-the-Loop Validation

To verify the performance of the proposed algorithm, a HIL experiment and even the real vehicle test is indispensable. Compared with real vehicle test, the HIL experiment can shorten the development time, accelerate the experiment setup process, and reduce the test cost. As such, the proposed strategy is validated through the HIL experiment. The validation platform of PHEV constructed in this research is based on the virtual scene, as shown in Fig. 17. The platform consists of five subsystems, including the virtual scene system, vehicle control system, real-time simulation system, data monitoring system, and driver operating system. The virtual scene ensures that the driver can drive the vehicle in an immersive driving environment. The data monitoring system built by the NI-Veristand is used to monitor important data. To attain high fidelity, the driver's operating system is constructed by a real driving equipment. The driver operating system receives the driver's command by the steering wheel, braking pedal and accelerator pedal.

The experiments in view of the traditional ECMS and proposed A-ECMS are conducted, and the related results are shown in Figs. 18 to 20 and Table V. Fig. 18 compares the EF variation. It can be observed that the proposed algorithm can dynamically control the EF, ranging from 3.38 to 2.45, according to the traffic

information. Fig. 19 shows the SOC trajectories with respect to different algorithms. Due to the unreasonable selection of the initial EF, the SOC based on the ECMS drops to the lower limit at 2000 s. By contrast, the A-ECMS can modulate the battery power by regulating the EF according to the traffic information, thus enabling the SOC to drop to 0.3 in the end of trip. As can also be seen, the proposed algorithm can regulate the EF to enable effective track of the reference SOC; however, both trajectories are slightly different in the beginning, and the difference becomes more apparent as the trip goes on. Fig. 20 compares the distribution of engine operating points. We can find that the engine operates in high efficiency region more intensively when A-ECMS is applied, compared to those of the ECMS. It is worth noting that, the fuel consumption of the ECMS and proposed A-ECMS in the HIL test is higher than that in the simulation validation. The discrepancy arises by the more drastic velocity induced by accelerator and brake pedal in the HIL test, as compared in Fig. 21. Table V lists the fuel consumption with two strategies, which illustrates that the total fuel consumption of the A-ECMS based on traffic information can be reduced by 6.01%, compared with the ECMS strategy. In the manner, the effectiveness of the proposed strategy is verified by the HIL experiment.

Fig. 17. EMS experiment platform of PHEV based on virtual scene.

Fig. 18. Comparison of the equivalent factors.

Fig. 19. Comparison of the SOC trajectory.

Fig. 20. Comparison of the distribution of engine working points.

Table V Comparison of the fuel consumption under the HIL test

	Fuel Consumption (kg)	Ending SOC	Corrected Fuel Consumption (kg)
ECMS	0.3898	0.3046	0.3811
A-ECMS	0.3618 (-7.18%)	0.3019 (-0.89%)	0.3582 (-6.01%)

Note: +: Increment; -: Reduction

Fig. 21. Comparison of the velocity curves.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an adaptive equivalent consumption minimization strategy is proposed to achieve the online energy management of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. The initial equivalent factor in terms of different initial state of charge and driving distance is searched by genetic algorithm. A simplified dynamic programming is employed to determine the reference state of charge trajectory based on the traffic information. The adaptive correction of equivalent factor is conducted by using a fuzzy controller to achieve precise tracking of the target trajectory. The hardware-in-the-loop platform based on virtual scene is developed to validate performance of the controller. Simulation and experimental results highlight that the proposed strategy can regulate the equivalent factor dynamically according to the traffic information, thus enabling effectively track of the reference SOC curve. The fuel consumption based on the adaptive equivalent consumption minimization strategy with the help of traffic information can be reduced by 6.01%, compared with the conventional equivalent consumption minimization strategy. The hardware-in-the-loop validation also manifests the capability of real-time operation of the proposed algorithm.

Next step work will focus on further performance improvement of the proposed algorithm considering time-varying traffic information. In addition, validation on the real vehicle test would also be our next step research focus in the future.

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